

FERGHANA-TASHKENT STATUS ROADS ARE AN IMPORTANT GROUP OF STATUS ART

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Abstract. This article talks about Fergana-Tashkent status roads, an important group of status art, local performance traditions.

Key words: Kashkarcha, Sokinoma, Wild Ushshaq, Bayot I-V, Chorgoh I-V, Gulyor-Shahnoz, Dugoh-Husayni.

СТАТУСНЫЕ ДОРОГИ ФЕРГАНА-ТАШКЕНТ ЯВЛЯЮТСЯ ВАЖНОЙ ГРУППОЙ СТАТУСНЫХ ПРОИЗВЕДЕНИЙ ИСКУССТВА

Аннотация. В этой статье рассказывается о статусных дорогах Фергана-Ташкент, важной группе статусного искусства, местных традициях исполнения.

Ключевые слова: Кашкарча, Со кинома, Видушак, Бает И-В, Моргах И-В, Гюлер-Шахноз, Дугах-Хусаини.

In Uzbek classical music, "Fergana-Tashkent statuses" or "Fergana-Tashkent statuses" are another main form of status art. In the Fergana Valley in the 19th and 20th centuries, the songs and musical instruments with and without series were widespread, they took the leading place in the oasis classical music heritage, and were infused with local performance traditions.

The Ferghana-Tashkent maqam song and instrument tracks, which have a large and small series, are close to a number of branches (sarahbor, savt), branches (kashkarcha, sokinoma) and series (the melodic movement of ulaming) in "Shashmaqom", similar in form, methods). Fergana-Tashkent status and status roads make up a series of 2, 3, 5 and 7 parts. Each of them has certain branches and is separated from each other by means of numbers.

Among the Ferghana-Tashkent maqams, there are large series of hymns: Bayot I-V, Chorgoh I-V, Gulyor-Shahnoz, Dugoh-Husayni I-VII (each part of the ulam is designated by general numerical numbers, except for the Gulyor-Shahnoz maqam), for example, Bayot 1, Bayot 2, Bayot 3, Bayot 4, Bayot 5. Major status among instrumental tracks (performed by soloist or instrumental ensemble); Chorgoh I-V; Miskin I-VII, Nasrullayi I-III, Navrozi novice songs I-III; Hajiniyaz I-II, Sumai status roads, etc. In addition to these, separate vocal and instrumental maqam works, as well as mature musicians and composers, were created in proportion to the branches and branches of "Shashmaqom" on the basis of songs, kata songs and instrumental tracks specific to the Fergana Valley.

For example, Wild Pasture, Wild Ushshaq, Wild Tanovar (singing and musical tracks), Desert Iraq, Tashkent Irogi, Kokan Irogi, Samarkand or Haji Abdulaziz Ushshogi, Tashkent or Mulla To 'ychi Ushshogi, Khojand or Sodir Khan Hafiz Ushshagi and others.

Ferghana-Tashkent statuses were formed in the melody, methods and forms of the branches, branches and taronas of the "Shashmaqom" singing department and developed based on the movement of the singing track. The first part is based on Sarahbor, the second part is based on his tarona or prose, the third part is savat, the fourth part is kashkarcha and the fifth part is based on sokinoma or ufar. Bayot, Chorgoh and Dugoh-Husayni maqoms were created on the basis of the branches of "Shashmaqom" named by these names ("Navo" and "Dugoh" maqoms), and

Gulyor-Shahnoz are branches of different maqoms ("Segoh" and "Rost" status) (five parts of this status have their own names: Gulyor, Shahnoz, Chapandozi Gulyor, Ushshaq and Ufari Gulyor). Gulyor-Shahnoz status is fundamentally different from other categories in terms of its structure. But Gulyor-Shahnoz's branches are more complex in terms of content and style, original songs of status. They are full of attractive, pleasant and impressive tones.

The series "Chorgoh" maqam consists of five parts and was created based on the Dugoh maqam branches of "Shashmaqom". Chorgoh 1, with its splendor and pleasantness, was created as a form of Dugoh sarahbori melody; but the development of the melody was shortened and certain changes were made to it. From the beginning to the climax (Muhayyari Chorgoh style is preserved) the direction and movement of the melody is similar to that of the leader (the circle method, tempo, and weight of the poem are preserved). Chorgoh 2 is a variant of Chorgoh style in Tarona style. Chorgoh 3 – It is said based on Chorgoh savtis, but its circle method and shape is simplified. Chorgoh 4 – Chorgoh savti is in the form of khashkarsha, and the theme, shape and circle method of the melody have been preserved. Chorgoh is in the 5th circle method, and its pace is much slower. But the performance style is characterized by its uniqueness.

Chorgoh maqam series is shortened from the branches of "Shashmaqom" adapted to the valley performance style (it becomes clear by the movement and development of the melody, the absence of the use of chords, the shortening of climaxes or the use of method options).

Ferghana-Tashkent maqams are widespread in traditional performance, and new versions of the ulam have been created by Uzbek composers, including Chorgoh VI (in the style of ufar) and Dugoh-Husaini VII-VIII (in the form of ufar and suporish) to Yunus Rajabi's work. belongs to Fergana-Tashkent Haji Abdulazaz Abdurasulov, Sodirkhan Hafiz Bobosharipov, Yunus Rajabi, Abdugadir Ismailov, Jorakhan Sultanov, Ma'murjon Uzokov, Imamjon Ikramov, Arifkhan Hotamov, Rasulqori Mamadaliyev, Ochilkhan Otakhanov, Abduhoshim Ismailov, Mahmudjon Tojiboyev and others were promoted in the promotion of their status. They greatly contributed to enriching them and creating new models.

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